

ADVANCES IN INTERACTIVE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AT ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Annotation. The purpose of the following article is to examine how technology is used to teach English in nations where it is not a first language. One of the best contemporary and technological approaches to learning a language is through interactive methods, which are particularly methodologically advantageous for the development of communicative competence in students at the stage of teaching foreign languages and for the formation of sustainable motivation, the development of cognitive interests in students at academic lyceums, intellectual skills of critical thinking, and abilities of self- and mutual aplomb.

Keywords: English, approach, communicative competence, development, learning, method, technological approaches, and education.

Introduction. First and foremost, the development of cutting-edge methods for teaching foreign languages is motivated by the need to resolve the current educational crisis, which would aid in the development of new types of professionals. Because the new XXI century places various advanced demands on university graduates more than the technocratic society of the XX century, the introduction of new technologies is also of utmost importance¹.

The teaching methods of the previous century, which were based on scientific logic and the tenet “from knowledge to skills”, should be replaced by methods based on the laws of students’ cognitive activity and orientation in the classroom, i.e. on the attainment by graduates of the pinnacles of professional, creative, spiritual, and moral other activities. All of this needed the expansion of the English language’s functions as an academic subject, taking into account the finest global experience in teaching English and the socio-cultural aspects of its study. It also created the task of teaching English in the country with fresh material. Today, in the practice of teaching languages of international communication, the tasks of teaching English as a means of intercultural communication, as a tool for the mutual enrichment of peoples, countries, and continents, and as a way to understand the accomplishments of national and universal culture, as a way for citizens of their country and members of the global community to understand themselves are important².

¹ Brophy, J. (2016). *Motivating Students to Learn*. New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates. (2nd edition).

² Craig, R. J., & Amernic, J. H. (2006). *Power Point presentation technology and the dynamics of teaching*.

The student's educational competence, or capacity to lead their learning activities, is strongly tied to the success of the development of communicative competence. The state educational standards reflect that the development of communicative ability is a requirement for the construction of students' professional competence. Language (linguistic), sociocultural, pragmatic, general educational, and compensating competencies can all be developed through effective communication.

Today's cutting-edge educational technology help with the task's resolution. At this stage in education, the following technologies are utilized in the practice of teaching foreign languages:

- cooperative learning;
- discussions;
- brain attacks (brainstorming);
- role-playing games of a problematic orientation;
- method of situational analysis (case study);
- method of projects;
- “Student portfolio” (E-Portfolio);
- Information Technology.

Currently, English instruction makes extensive use of the aforementioned technology. Therefore, crucial abilities required for the development of communication and sociocultural competencies include the ability to lead a discussion, defend one's point of view with arguments, explain one's thoughts succinctly, and the ability to listen and hear an opponent. The final lessons in English language lessons on oral practice frequently talk about the issues surrounding a particular subject. But, etc., teaching a foreign language is important. Some lyceum students prepare their arguments for a discussion topic in advance. Students are typically split into two groups (small cooperation groups with approximately 5 members in each group) to argue different points of view on the selected subject. In lyceums, students first have a preliminary discussion in small groups, and only then do they have a broad discussion³.

Additionally, to do this type of work (discussion) successfully, preparation work must be done. This includes teaching students how to hold a conversation and how to select strong arguments. A brainstorming strategy is employed in the initial stages. The group then has a debate about each student's proposal after it has been written down on the board without further discussion. If the student's justification is strong enough, the argument is kept for further discussion; otherwise, it is eliminated. Recapitulating the

³ Freeman, D. L. (2000). Techniques and principles in language teaching. New York: Oxford University Press.

conversation is crucial. Each student is evaluated using a rating system to maintain and motivate their activity during the discussion. The technological chart of the teaching materials for a practical foreign language course specifies the maximum amount of points that a student may obtain for this kind of task.

Through this practice, they learn that they can speak about their world in English, which enhances their capacity for thought. The use of an interactive method fosters the development of flexible thinking while also providing an environment that is conducive to solving creative problems. Students share their opinions and learn how to support them⁴. Contradictions may arise as students learn to communicate with one another during interactive skill acquisition. the entire educational process, which is based on an interactive method and is defined by students' activity during the session. In conclusion, we can state that the interactive and advanced approach's major goal is the development of speaking abilities, particularly in ensuring cooperative activities and boosting student enthusiasm. These interactive learning methods aids in the efficient assimilation of course material⁵. The most productive and successful method for teaching a foreign language is thought to be an interactive one. He aids in easing the challenges that arise during the learning process. Because of this, the majority of scientists and educators tend to believe that interactive learning methods are becoming more and more important. The teaching system has altered over the past few decades in tandem with the significant changes that have occurred in every aspect of human life. It is especially important to improve and do research on foreign language teaching.

Traditional teaching techniques including the grammar-translation method, audio-lingual instruction, and direct instruction have declined in popularity and been replaced with unconventional ones. It can help kids attain goals, improve communication among themselves, and develop all of their skills. The major goal of these modifications is to deliver lessons that are learner-centered rather than teacher-centered. The function of group work activities has a place in this situation. The various ways that students and the teacher might engage in class are known as interaction patterns in the teaching of English. Using the proper interaction pattern is the key to succeeding in class⁶.

⁴ Koksál, D. (2004). Benefits of project work in ELT, Palacký University in Olomouc, Supervisor: PhDr. Sabina Pazderová Olomouc 2008.

⁵ Khasanova, G. K. (2021). Main trends in the development of education and professional training in the world. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, (Special Issue 1), 257-262.

⁶ Fried-Booth, D., L. (2002). Project work (2nd ed.). New York: Oxford University Press.

Four different interaction patterns exist group work, pair work, full class working, and individual work. The activity is assigned separately, and this form of work is advantageous for pupils who do not wish to converse with or solicit the opinions of others. Students who work independently develop the independence to reason independently, work at their own pace rather than needing to adjust for their group members, and become more confident acting independently. But there are some drawbacks of this kind as well: less communication and reduced student speech; certain students, especially extroverts, may feel a little alone in solo work. When the assigned activity or assignment is provided to two pupils, it is called pair work. Together, they can complete the assignment, and the solution is provided by a partner. The teacher may monitor how hard each couple is working and inspire the class as a whole.

Conclusion. Therefore, interactive methods expose students to a variety of linguistic components and functions. Children are more emotionally and academically engaged while working in a group. They must reflect, participate in the group, assess what others have to say, share information, receive clarification from friends, and work as a team to produce a presentation. In order to increase fluency, students use and experiment with the language they already know. They also use some pre-taught material from the teacher or material given by group members to express themselves more fully and raise the standard of their performance.

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